

Istisna' on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the mapping of research topics around the Istisna' contracts in the Islamic Financial Inclusion using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and library research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Istisna' contracts; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization regarding the Istisna' contracts based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the Istisna' contract using a library research study. The results of the study show that: (1) based on the mapping of the distribution of journal publications, there are 52 journal publications regarding the Istisna' contracts; (2) based on VOSviewer's bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around the Istisna' contracts are divided into 8 clusters and 201 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of library research studies, there are 4 main topics surrounding the Istisna' contracts. The difference between this research and previous research is that this study explains and maps all research topics around the Istisna' contract so that future researchers can find the research gaps around the Istisna' contracts. The implications and contribution of this research are that there is a mapping of research topics around the Istisna' contract, which is often or rarely researched by researchers to be a reference for future researchers.

Keywords: Istisna'; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Inclusion

Introduction

Every human being cannot be separated from buying and selling activities. In Islam, buying and selling is an activity of exchanging goods carried out using certain contracts. However, in a buying and selling transaction, goods that are not available often cause the buying and selling activity to be cancelled. Therefore, to overcome this, Islam enforces the Istisna' Agreement.

In the current era of globalization, Islamic banks have become one of the Islamic financial industries that is in demand by the public. Sharia banking has three main products, namely funds distribution products, fund collection, and services provided to its customers (Admaja, 2016). One of the fund distribution products offered by sharia banks is Istisna'. The Istisna' contract is a contract that has a big influence on sharia banking. The greater the financing channeled to customers by sharia banks, the greater the profits obtained by sharia banking. The provisions of the Istisna' Agreement are regulated in the DSN-MUI Fatwa Number 06/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning the sale and purchase of Istisna'.

Based on searches via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital), there are already many researchers who have conducted research on the Istisna' Agreement. There were 53 studies of the Istisna' Agreement from 2014 to 2022. In several studies, researchers discussed the Istisna' Agreement more in sharia banking. Istisna' contracts are also often combined with other sharia banking products such as Salam contracts, Ijarah contracts, Murabahah contracts, and others.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around the Istisna' card in the Sharia Finance Industry in Indonesia by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains and maps all research topics surrounding the Istisna' card, so that future researchers can find out the gaps in research surrounding the Istisna' card. The implication and contribution of this research is that there is a mapping of research topics around the Hawalah card which are often or rarely studied by researchers, so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

Literature Review

The Istisna' contract is a sale and purchase transaction by making a prior order (PO). The goods ordered must comply with the qualifications and requirements agreed upon by both parties, namely the buyer (mustashni') and the manufacturer/seller (shani'). The form and amount of the payment instrument used in the Istisna' Agreement must be known. The means of payment can be money, goods or benefits (National Sharia Council Fatwa No: 06/DSN-MUI/IV/2000).

Bibliometrics is a quantitative method used to calculate, observe and analyze scientific literature studies (Roemer & Borchardt, 2015). This is one type of quantitative analysis used in the production observation process for academic literature. A bibliometric approach is used to assess the influence of a research, field, over time which is carried out to determine the relationship between influence and impact as well as participation and relevance to published literature. VOSviewer is software used to construct and visualize bibliometric networks. Bibliometric networks can consist of studies, journals, or individual publications, or they can also be a combination of bibliographies, co-citations, or co-authorship relationships.

Library research is a search and research of literature taken from various sources such as journals, books and other publications. These sources must have a correlation with the topic being researched, so that they can produce several sentences related to one particular polemic or topic.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research studies. The object of the research is the Istisna' contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Istisna' contracts in the Sharia Financial Industry.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Istisna' " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications surrounding the Istisna' agreement using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around the Istisna' agreement using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the Istisna' contract using a library research study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the Istisna' Agreement in the Sharia Financial Industry

There are 52 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2013 to 2022. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the Istisna' contract by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2013	1	2017	4	2020	7
2014	3	2018	6	2021	17
2015	1	2019	4	2022	8
2016	1	Amount			52

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 2 journal publishing industries that publish more journals about Istisna' contract research, namely Al-Tsaman: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance and Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, each with 2 articles.

Table 2. Affiliation/Industry of journal publishers regarding the Istisna' Agreement

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
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Al-Tsaman: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, Journal of Islamic Economics and Business	2
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Accounting and Management Journal, Ad-Deenar: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Adzkiya: Journal of Sharia Law and Economics, AKM-Action to the Community, AKTSAR: Journal of Sharia Accounting, ACCOUNTABILITY, Al-Azhar Journal of Islamic Economics, Al-Ihda': Journal of Education and Thought, Al-Insyiroh: Journal of Islamic Studies, Al-Intaj: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Al-Kharaj: Journal of Sharia Economics, Finance & Business, Al-Muamalat: Journal of Sharia Economics, Al-Muqayyad, Al-Tsaman : Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, At-Taradhi: Journal of Economic Studies, Az-Zarqa': Journal of Islamic Business Law, CASHFLOW: Current Advanced Research On Sharia Finance and Economic Worldwide, DIKTUM: Journal of Sharia and Law, Diwan: Journal of Arabic Language and Literature, Business Economics, Islamic Economics, EKSYA: Journal of Sharia Economics, EL-BANAT: Journal of Islamic Thought and Education, Al-Furqania : Journal of Ushuluddin and Islamic Sciences, Health Research Policy and Systems, Ibn Abbas: Journal of Al-Quran and Tafsir Sciences, Indonesian Interdisciplinary Journal of Sharia Economics (IIJSE), Indonesian Journal of Academic Librarianship, International Journal of Islamic Economics, Intiqad: Journal of Religion Islam and Islamic Education, Islamic Circle, Journal of Applied Islamic Economics and Finance, Accounting Journal, AKUNESA Accounting Journal, Accounting and Management Journal, Dimamu Journal, Journal of Business Economics, Journal of Islamic Economics, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, EMBA Journal, Journal Ilmiah Edunomika, Ilmiah Islamic Economics Journal, Ilmiah Tarbiyah Umat Journal, International Journal of Islamic Economics, Journal of Management and Finance, Journal of Accounting Masters, Journal of Islamic Education and Thought, Journal of Accounting and Business Research, Journal of Islamic Law Sharia, Tabarru' Journal: Islamic Banking and Finance, Khasanah Ilmu: Journal of Tourism and Culture, Khazanah Multidisciplinary, LAA MAISYIR: Journal of Islamic Economics, Maro: Journal of Sharia Economics and Business, Media Librarian, Muamalatuna: Journal of Sharia Economic Law, Mubeza, Muhazabatuna: Journal of Sharia Accounting, Nursing Current, SERAMBI: Journal of Management Economics and Islamic Business, Syarikat: Journal of the Sharia Economic Family, Syntax Literate.

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Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Furthermore, all researchers only wrote 1 journal article about the Istisna' contract in the Sharia Financial Industry. They are: Abrar, Izul Abdillah, Arman Paramansyah, Dessy Damayanthi, Nihayatun Nafisah, Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha, Taudlikhul Afkar, Teguh Purwanto, Dewi Wulan Sari, Mohamad Yusak Anshori, Muhammad Ardi, Muhammad Rizki Hidayah, Kholil

- Cluster 1. The color red consists of 45 topics, namely : advantage, agreement, aster village ciwastra sharia mortgage, bai, business actor, buyer, cancellation, case, cash, cash price, concept, condition, consumer, cutomer, delay, DSN MUI IV, DSN MUI No, fact, implementation, interest, islamic law, istishna contract, item, khiyar, late payment, library research, musly group convection, order, orders transaction, palima grand city, palima grand city sharia housing, payment, payment mechanism, payment system, pillar, practice, price, PT Royal Bridea Indonesia, purchase contract, sale, sharia housing, specification, system, term, yuda welding workshop.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 34 topics, namely : academic, contract, bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Muamalat Polewali Mandar, Bank Syariah Bukopin, business, business person, buying, descriptive qualitative research, informant, information, interview, Islamic perspective, buying and selling, using PSAK provisions, methods, online buying, financing home, application of transactions, influence of murabahah financing, distribution of funds, principles, problems, sharia banking products, PSAK, PSAK No, qualitative method, requirements, risks and advantages, selling transactions, about istishna accounting, transactions.
- Cluster 3. The dark blue color consists of 34 topics, namely : BJB Syariah Bank, BJB Syariah Bank, descriptive analysis, financial service authority, financial statement, fluctuation, ijarah financing income, influence, Islamic commercial bank, istishna financing, istishna financing income, margin income, Muamalat Indonesia bank, multiple linear regression, murabahah, murabahah financing, net income, net profit, object, period, population, positive effect, purposive sampling, sample, sampling method, significant effect, bank sharia, t count, t table, tcount, third party fund, value.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 26 topics, namely : category, covid, descriptive, DSN, DSN MUI, existence, fatwa, fatwa DSN MUI, hadith, Islamic bank, selling, legal basis, legal basis, legality, muamalah, observation, pandemic, Islamic banking, provision, purchase, qualitative research, qur, salam, salam and istishna.
- Cluster 5. Light purple consists of 20 topics, namely : asset, BPRS, competitive advantage, consumer loyalty, data, data analysis technique, f test, ijarah financing, impact, normality test, PT Bank BRI Syariah tbk, qardh financing, quantitative study, relationship marketing, return, ROA, sample size, second hand data, t test, validity.
- Cluster 6. Light blue consists of 17 topics, namely : application, craftsman, documentation, field research, Islamic economic value, istishna, istishna contract, library research, muamalah fiqh, observation, seller, place, plisket convection business, process, secondary data, seller, specifications.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 14 topics, namely : bank, Bank Indonesia, Bank Syariah Mandiri, Syairah Commercial Bank, BRI Syariah, ijara, ijarah, Islamic bank, istishna, mudaraba, mudarabah, murabah, musharaka, profitability
- Cluster 8. Dark purple consists of 11 topics, namely : alternative contract, company, contract, developer, financing, international capital

market, Islamic banking, istishna financing, primary data, sukuk, sukuk issuance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Application of the Istisna' Agreement in Buying and Selling Transactions

There are 7 studies on this topic, that is:

- (a) Application to the Sharia Finance Industry. The research object is: 14 sharia banks. This research uses a descriptive quantitative approach. Data collection techniques using Sharia Bank financial report data. Data analysis technique using paired-sample t-test. The research findings on this topic are: there was an increase in public interest in Istisna' financing during the Covid-19 pandemic than before.
- (b) Its application to trade in handicraft goods. The research uses a qualitative phenomenological approach based on observation, interview and documentation techniques. The first research finding, namely: the practice of Istisna' contracts occurs between collectors and silver craftsmen. The object of the research is: Kotagede Yogyakarta silver crafts. Silver craftsmen act as shani', collectors act as mustashni', handicraft items as mashnu', ra'sul mal /capital comes from down payments from collectors and craftsmen, then sighah ijab wa qabul/ a verbal and written handover of the contract in the form of a note. The remaining payment is received by the craftsman when he finishes working on the order according to the initial agreement. The second research finding, namely: the practice of Istisna' contracts among songko recca craftsmen is in accordance with sharia principles, both in applying Islamic economic values, as well as in applying the principles of justice, blessing and honesty in their business. So, there is added value in business, both in terms of material, mental and spiritual. The third research finding, namely: the practice of Istisna' contracts in the CV Bina Karya furniture industry, Makassar City. Here, the orderer pays a down payment of 50% and the remainder is paid when the object of the order has been delivered to the orderer's house, by attaching a purchase invoice. So, in general, the transactions are in accordance with sharia principles. The fourth research finding, namely: its application to buying and selling furniture at Batenese Furniture is in accordance with sharia principles. There is a down payment on the payment method, then if the order object has been received by the customer, then there will be repayment. And it is also rare for unilateral contract cancellations to occur in this company.
- (c) Application to buying and selling canoes. The research object is: Simpang Gaung Village, Gaung District, Indragiri Hilir Regency. The research method uses a qualitative approach in the nature of field research. The research findings on this topic are: there is damage to the contract caused by discrepancies, both in terms of specifications and criteria for the canoe ordered at the beginning of the contract. On the part of the buyer, there is no right to choose whether to reject the order or not, but the canoe maker decides unilaterally that everything ordered must be paid in full when the canoe is finished.
- (d) Its application is to buying and selling building equipment. The object of the research is: Mibel Barokah, Kebun Hamlet, East Pademawu Village, Pademawu District, Pamekasan Regency. This research uses a

qualitative field approach. The data used is primary and secondary. Data collection techniques, namely observation, interviews and documentation. The research findings on this topic are: the Istisna' contract in this case is in accordance with sharia principles, both in terms of ordering procedures, manufacturing processes and delivery of goods. Researchers recommend that companies always act responsibly and honestly so that there is no damage to contracts and can increase consumer confidence in the company.

- (e) Implementation of the Parallel Istisna' contract. The research object is: PT. Berkah Rangga Sakti, Bangkalan District, Bangkalan Regency. This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach. Data collection techniques use observation, documentation and interviews, with random sampling. The research findings in this topic are: its application in buying and selling houses where there are no fines if there is a delay in installment payments, the down payment can be paid in installments and the house that is put up as collateral for this financing. If the consumer dies, then he is freed from all debts or considered paid off by the company. In general, the implementation of the Parallel Istisna' contract in this transaction is in accordance with sharia principles.
- (f) Application to buying and selling houses/mortgages. The research uses a qualitative descriptive-analysis approach based on the field. The first research finding, namely: its application to the Indonesian Islamic Housing Company, Bogor, West Java. Istisna' and Bai' Taqsith transactions are carried out without intermediary sharia banks. There are differences in the transactions therein, namely: the company sets a margin of 7% of the original price, there are no fines for late payment of installments, deliberation is held if there is a consumer default and consumers can design the house they want themselves. This case can provide lessons for the public regarding the original form of credit/taqsith transactions. The second and third research findings, namely: application to the company Housing Alam Desa Ketidur Mojokerto and Developer Property Syariah Bogor. The concept is that there is no interest, no fines and the collateral is in the form of goods owned by the consumer, not land/building documents that are being paid in installments. If consumers are unable to pay, the land and buildings will be executed by the company. If the consumer dies, the payment is passed on to the heirs. If there are no heirs, the company will write off the debt.
- (g) Application to online buying and selling. The research objects are: business people, consumers, academics and ulama in Tasikmalaya City. The research uses a qualitative approach based on case studies. Measuring sales and purchases uses the standards of the Sharia Accounting Standards Board of the Indonesian Accountants Association (DSAS IAI) based on the provisions of PSAK Syariah 104. The findings in this research are: the implementation of the Istisna' agreement between the seller and the buyer is in accordance with sharia principles, but in terms of recording and accounting it is not in accordance with PSAK Syariah 104 guidelines. So, there needs to be important attention for regulators in the accounting sector to pay closer attention to the online buying and selling business that has been happening in society.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Influence of the Istisna' Agreement

There are 3 studies on this topic, namely:

- (a) Its influence on company profitability. The research uses a quantitative approach with multiple linear regression analysis methods. The analysis tool uses the SPSS/ E-Views computer program with the classic assumption test method, which consists of normality, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation tests. The sampling technique uses purposive sampling. The first research finding, namely: Istisna' financing partially has a positive and significant effect on the profitability of Sharia People's Financing Banks/BPRS for the 2013-2017 period. The second research finding, namely: partial Istisna' financing has no significant effect on Return On Equity /ROE of Bank Syariah Bukopin, BRI Syariah, Bank Syariah Mandiri and Bank Muamalat Indonesia for the period March 2015-August 2016. The third research finding, namely: Istisna' financing partially, it has no significant effect on the profitability of BCA Syariah, BNI Syariah, BRI Syariah, BJB Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Maybank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Syariah Mandiri and Bank Victoria Syariah for the 2015-2018 period. The fourth research finding, namely: partial Istisna' financing has no significant effect on the profitability of Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Syariah Mandiri, BRI Syariah and BJB Syariah for the period 2011:Q1-2015:Q4. The fifth research finding, namely: Istisna' financing partially has a positive and significant effect on Return On Assets / ROA at Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Mandiri Syariah and BRI Syariah for the 2009-2013 period.
- (b) The effect on fund distribution income. The research object is: Bank Syariah Bukopin. This research uses a quantitative descriptive verification approach. Data analysis techniques use regression, correlation, coefficient of determination, hypothesis testing, t test and f test with SPSS software. The research findings on this topic are: partial Istisna' financing does not have a significant effect on fund distribution income.
- (c) The effect on company profits. The research object is: Bank Muamalat Indonesia. This research uses a descriptive quantitative approach, with multiple regression analysis. The research findings on this topic are: Istisna' financing has an insignificant positive effect on company profits.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Juridical Study of the Istisna' Agreement

There are 6 studies on this topic, namely:

- (a) Istisna' Agreement in the Koran and Hadith. Research findings on this topic are: first, Surah Al-Baqarah verse 275; secondly, the hadith narrated by Al-Tirmidziy from 'Amr bin 'Auf Al-Muzaniy, which is also contained in the book Al-Mustadrak 'Ala Al-Shahihain Al-Hakim Vol. 4, 113; third, the hadith narrated by Ibn Majah and Al-Daruquthniy from Abu Sa'id Al-Khudriy; fourth, narrated hadith; fourth, the agreement of the ulama through ijmak that the Istisna' contract is permissible in accordance with the pillars and conditions; fifth, the rule of fiqh " The original law of all forms of muamalat is permissible/permissible, unless there is an argument that forbids it"; sixth, fatwa no. 06/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning buying and selling of Istisna'; seventh, Law no. 7/92 in conjunction with Law no. 10 of 1998; eighth, Appendix 6: BI

Decree No. 32/34/SK dated 12/05/99 Director of BI; ninth, rule no. 6/17/PBI/2004 Article 34; tenth, rule no. 6/24/PBI/2004 Article 36; regulation no. 7/46/PBI/2005 Articles 15, 16, 17; eleventh, Surah Al-Kahf verses 94-95 which comes from the fatwa of the Islamic Affairs and Charitable Activities Department of Dubai Number 29140.

- (b) Parallel Istisna' Agreement in the Koran and Hadith. Research findings on this topic are: first, Surah Al-Baqarah verse 282; second, the hadith narrated by Imam Bukhari from Sahal No. 2381; third, fatwa no. 22/DSN-MUI/III/2002 concerning parallel Istisna' buying and selling.
- (c) Istisna' contract in muamalah fiqh. This research uses a qualitative approach with library research methodology which is presented analytically and descriptively. Research findings on this topic, namely: the meaning of Istisna' buying and selling, its legal basis, its pillars, conditions, termination of the contract, parallel Istisna' consequences and its application in the Sharia Financial Industry. The principles in an Istisna' contract are: the principle of ibahah /allowance, the principle of hurriyyah al-ta'aqud/ freedom of contract, the principle of ridhaiyyah /consensualism, the principle of iltizam /attachment, the principle of tawazun /balance, the principle of benefit, the principle of trust, the principle of 'is /justice.
- (d) Parallel Istisna' Agreement in muamalah fiqh. Research findings on this topic are: first, the meaning; second, the legal basis; third, the pillars of the contract (buyer, seller, object and agreement); fourth, the conditions (the two contracts must be separate and they must not depend on each other/ ta'alluq); fifth, there are three payment systems (upfront payment, upon delivery of goods or deferred); sixth, the end of the contract.
- (e) Consumer protection in the Istisna' contract. The research object is: Musly Group Convection. The research method is descriptive and field, using a qualitative approach. Data collection techniques, namely: observation, interviews and documentation. Research findings on this topic are: there is a delay in what was ordered in advance, resulting in losses for consumers. The legal basis that can be used in this problem is: Article 27 of Law no. 8 of 1999 concerning consumer protection. The implementation of the contract complies with the sharia principles of the Istisna' contract, but because there is a delay, this contract is false and compensation is needed in the transaction.
- (f) Financing accounting is based on Istisna'. The research in this case used a descriptive-analytic qualitative approach. Data collection techniques using literature and the field. The first research finding, namely: its application to the Muamalat Institute (Bank Muamalat Polewali Mandar). The company has carried out accounting treatment of Istisna' contracts based on PSAK No. 59 and PAPSI 2003, including presentation, recognition, disclosure and measurement. The second research finding, namely: its application to Bank Syariah Bukopin KC Semarang, is that it is in accordance with PSAK 104.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Other Issues Related to the Istisna' Agreement

There are 4 studies on this topic, namely:

- (a) Risk management in the Istisna' contract. The findings in this research are: first, it lists the limits of customers who can apply for financing,

through the character of the prospective debtor, the prospective debtor's financial capacity, capital or productive assets owned by the prospective debtor, collateral or guarantees or assets of the prospective debtor. debtors who have economic value, conditions of economy /economic and financial conditions of prospective debtors, constraints /obstacles or problems that may occur to prospective debtors; second, the financing limit/ ceiling is adjusted to the Maximum Credit Granting Limit/BMPK Number 30 Article 9; third, there are provisions for payment of down payments/DP by prospective debtors; fourth, risk mitigation tools can minimize risks that may be carried out by debtors.

- (b) Hawalah and Istisna' contract. The findings in this research are: there are supporting factors for this transaction, from commitment, management, mentality, good trust by leaders, employees, staff. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factors come from customers' lack of understanding of this contract and the lack of online and offline interbank network services.
- (c) Cancellation of sale of Istisna'. This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach based on library research (library research). The data source uses secondary data. The findings in this research are: based on the DSN-MUI fatwa, cancellation of the Istisna' contract is permitted if there is a defect in the object of the order, or one of the pillars and conditions of the Istisna' contract is not fulfilled. Another condition, namely: there is agreement between both parties, the orderer and the buyer, so that no loss occurs to either party, as in Surah Al-Nisa' verse 29.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications surrounding the Istisna' agreement in the Sharia Finance Industry during the period 2013 to 2022, originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there were 52 published journal articles. Second, based on Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer bibliometric studies, the results of network visualization around the Istisna' contract The Sharia Finance Industry is divided into 8 clusters and 201 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 45 topics, cluster 2 consists of 34 topics, cluster 3 consists of 34 topics, cluster 4 consists of 26 topics, cluster 5 consists of 20 topics, cluster 6 consists of 17 topics, cluster 7 consists of 14 topics, and cluster 8 consists of 11 topics. Third, based on Mapping Research Topics using library research studies, there are 4 topics related to the Istisna' contract in the Sharia Financial Industry, namely: (1) Application of the Istisna' Agreement in Buying and Selling Transactions; (2) The influence of the Istisna' Agreement; (3) Juridical Study of the Istisna' Agreement; and (4) Other Issues Relating to the Istishna Contract.

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